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ABBREVIATIONS

ATU	:	Atlantic Technological University
BMI	:	Business Model Innovation
BUU	:	Bursa Uludag University
CA	:	Consortium Agreement
CS	:	Civil Society
EC	:	European Commission
FWCI	:	Field-Weighted Citation Impact
IN-BP	:	Industry and Business Partners
IO	:	International Organisations
IP	:	Intellectual Property
IPR	:	Intellectual Property Rights
PC	:	Project Coordinator
PH	:	Project Handbook
PM	:	Policymakers
PSC	:	Research and Scientific Communities
P&I	:	Research and Innovation
SMEs	:	Small and Medium- Sized Enterprises
ULE	:	Universidad de Leon
WP:		Work Packages

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Successful and widespread dissemination, communication and exploitation (DEC) is strategic to showcase the results and impact of the goals and objectives within the REMODEL project. The project will use this plan as a guideline for conducting its communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. These activities are presented to be carried out by the REMODEL consortium during the lifetime of the project. This plan covers a range of DEC activities necessary for the project and also acts as the deliverable of WP5.

The plan covers the promotion of communication and dissemination activities, the expectations from the exploitation activities planned within the scope of the post-project, the expected impacts on the target audiences and stakeholders, and key performance indicators of the activities. The plan consists of 6 main sections. The first section is the project visual identity which contains information on the project logo, template, typography, etc. Another part is the dissemination plan covering dissemination activities aimed at increasing the benefits stakeholders provide from project results. The third part is the communication plan that includes the necessary activities and tools to introduce the project to all internal and external stakeholders. The exploitation plan, which will ensure the sustainability of the project after its completion, is also presented. IP protection and monitoring dissemination and communication activities are clarified.

The plan will undergo an internal review every six months to ensure maximum effectiveness. Furthermore, in the scope of WP5, D5.2 Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, Liaison, and Clustering Report will be prepared at M18 (draft) and M36 (final) for ensuring the monitoring process of DEC. Therefore, this is a work-in-progress plan and not a final document.

1. ABOUT THE REMODEL PROJECT

Funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101079203, REMODEL is part of the Widening Participation and Spreading Excellence action that aims to strengthen the R&I capacity and skills of Bursa Uludag University (BUU) by leveraging the experience, state-of-the-art knowledge and tools of twinning partners Universidad de Leon (ULE) and Atlantic Technological University (ATU). Thus, BUU will enhance its research profile in innovative business models and gain advanced skills for the management and administration of EU R&I programs through the implementation of training and networking programs in REMODEL. An extensive scientific strategy will be formulated, which will involve the exchange of personnel, the establishment of collaborative research and innovation programs pertaining to Business Model Innovation (BMI), and the establishment of an international master's program in hospitality sector management. Therefore in order to achieve the project's objectives, it is of great importance to communicate and disseminate project results to all stakeholders in the value chain during the project period.

REMODEL's work plan has been structured into five work packages (WP) that are consistent with the project's concept and goals. There is coordination among all WPs. However, the WP5 ensures the visibility and sustainability of project activities across all other work packages (WPs). The main aim of the WP5 is to define a common strategy for communicating REMODEL outcomes and disseminating its results to maximise the project exploitation and ensure that project outcomes effectively reach REMODEL target audience and key stakeholders. WP5 includes dissemination and communication, exploitation, liaison and clustering activities and R&I policy recommendations. WP5, aims to ensure that stakeholders are aware of all activities, results and opportunities for participation and interaction with the REMODEL project. Additionally, it provides an opportunity for partners to enhance their standing in the scientific community, obtain economic advantages, and potentially draw in users of the project outcomes. REMODEL's DEC plan lays the foundation for promoting and disseminating the project's outcomes, as well as supporting the strategy for reaching stakeholders.

Figure 1. REMODEL WP5 Activities

According to the REMODEL dissemination and communication strategy, this plan is a living document that will be updated to ensure the effectiveness of measures proposed, to include new dissemination/communication-related actions, when necessary, to enlarge the stakeholders' map with new target audiences according to the project evolution.

2. TARGET AUDIENCE

The target audience refers to the specific group of people or organisations that the project aims to reach, engage, or impact with its outputs or outcomes. The target audience may include different stakeholders, such as beneficiaries, end-users, customers, partners, investors, regulators, or the wider community, depending on the nature and scope of the project. Identifying and understanding the target audience is crucial for the success of a project, as it helps to tailor the project objectives, activities, and communication strategies to the audience's specific needs, interests, and expectations. This increases the likelihood of achieving the project results' intended impact, adoption, and sustainability.

In the REMODEL project, the target audience has been determined initially for the right interaction. Then the appropriate dissemination and communication channels and tools have been selected. A preliminary analysis of the target audience, and proposed measures to reach them, have already been developed. Thus effective communication and engagement with the project target audience are also crucial for the dissemination of project results and the achievement of the project objectives. The analysis of the stakeholders in the target audience has special importance for the project.

2.1. Stakeholder Analysis

For the successful dissemination of the project, it is necessary to constantly interact and collaborate with the stakeholders. Stakeholders who have a vested interest in the project may be affected by its outcomes or decisions. Stakeholders are considered important to the success of a project and it is essential to engage with them and manage their expectations throughout the project lifecycle.

The stakeholder analysis will be continuously conducted based on existing and additional stakeholder groups (if any). The interests or conflicts of interest of stakeholders will be taken into account with regard to the objectives of the project. Additionally, relationships will be established between different stakeholders to determine ways of working together for the project. The stakeholder analysis determines how the project will be affected by various stakeholders and how it will affect them.

Thus, it can be evaluated how effectively the project results are disseminated and what additional efforts are needed to reach the target audience. The table below has been prepared to report the stakeholder information of the project. The table will be filled by all partners as an internal project document. In this respect, it is an important tool that ensures the coordination of the consortium in internal communication.

Table 1. Stakeholder Table

Partner institution	Stakeholder Name	Internal Or External Stakeholder	Contact Person Phone, Email, Website, Address	Behaviour Unaware, Resistant, Neutral, Supportive, or Leading?	Impact How much does the project impact them? (Low, Medium, High)	Influence How much influence do they have over the project? (Low, Medium, High)	What does this stakeholder need?	What is important to the stakeholder?	How could the stakeholder contribute to the project?	How could the stakeholder block the project?	Strategy for engaging the stakeholder

With the identification of stakeholders, the stakeholder matrix will be prepared. The stakeholder matrix is a project management tool that assists in assessing the various stakeholders involved in a project and determining the most effective approach to align their priorities with the project's objectives. As each stakeholder or group may have distinct requirements, the matrix enables determining the optimal strategy for each group.

Table 2. Stakeholder Analysis Matrix

INFLUENCE	HIGH	KEEP SATISFIED		MANAGE CLOSELY	
	LOW	MONITOR (MINIMUM EFFORT)		KEEP INFORMED	
LOW			HIGH		
INTEREST					

2.2. Target Groups

After determining the target audience all dissemination and communication materials and other project outputs are tailored to specific target groups to generate interest, attract the attention of all stakeholders and citizens, and maximise project impact. The target group is more closely linked to the objectives and outcomes of the project. To ensure the success of REMODEL, dissemination activities are tailored to each target group by using different dissemination channels and materials, conveying the project messages most appropriately, and identifying adequate exploitation pathways. The target group refers to the group of people or organisations that the project aims to directly benefit or impact, and it is an essential concept in project management, development, and evaluation. The target group of the REMODEL project which varies according to different DEC tools, as follows.

Policymakers (PM): Organisations, institutions and individuals that are responsible for the formulation, amendment and application of policies and regulations. They can be local, regional, national or international. Within the scope of this project, interaction with national authorities, regional authorities and local authorities regarding the proposed BMI Lab, R&I incentives and policy implementations is important. Project results can be enhanced by informing these authorities of specific outcomes that could enrich R&I Plans and by receiving feedback on the relevance of the results. In particular, support will be provided by BUU Technology Transfer Office (TTO) and relevant ministries and directorates for the establishment of the voucher system.

Research and Scientific Communities (RSC): The research and scientific community is a diverse network of interacting scientists. These are groups of academics, researchers, students and practitioners searching for common knowledge. Academic staff and researchers, as the key end users of project results, need access to applications, tools, materials and training activities to be used in the project to create innovative business models and improve operational procedures and methodologies. Within the scope of the project, they will provide the sustainability of the project by transferring their knowledge about the implementation of innovative business models to the enterprises. At the same time, the project results will be included in the master's and doctoral course plans. Thus, students will be able to benefit from REMODEL results in their education life.

Research and Scientific Communities (RSC): The International associations and organisations such as EU institutions and other EU-supported projects will be contacted during the project implementation to act as multipliers to increase the number of stakeholders who will be aware of project activities and results, encouraging them to adopt project developments, improve policies and use project results. It is also important for exploitation that these stakeholders embrace the project developments and encourage them to use the project results.

Industry and Business Partners (IN-BP): The BMI Lab to be created within the scope of the project is an important opportunity for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the hospitality sector. In this direction, it is expected that REMODEL will become widespread in the sector by sharing the project outputs. In addition, collaborations with businesses in the sector will also contribute to the project results. There will be SMEs requesting to benefit from the voucher system with the completion of the project. These businesses, which benefit from BUU BMI Lab activities, will ensure the project's sustainability.

Civil Society (CS): Many project activities will also be shared with non-governmental organisations, informal groups and citizens in order to disseminate the project in a more resilient and sustainable way by raising awareness about REMODEL goals and tools.

In order to reach the determined target groups, the following questions have been answered:

- How to reach target groups easily and efficiently?
- Which target groups should be reached using which dissemination channel?
- Which message do we want to convey to which target groups?
- How can the target groups be encouraged to further engage in the REMODEL project?
- How to build a national or EU-wide stakeholder network to expand the impact of the REMODEL project?

3. DISSEMINATION PLAN

In the most general terms, dissemination is the public disclosure of project results by appropriate means without violating intellectual property and personal rights.

In the REMODEL dissemination plan, targeted dissemination activities are proposed so that the information collected in the project and the main outputs of the project can be used in different ways to help achieve the highest possible impact on the project results. Project results will be presented in different formats and channels in line with the needs of target groups. At the beginning of the project, the corporate identity of the project will be designed, and integration will be ensured in the project process.

REMODEL dissemination activities are not limited to awareness and understanding goals. In addition, it is planned to provide a high level of participation and support to the dissemination activities and results. REMODEL also aims to establish strong ties with key actors and stakeholders as well as other relevant initiatives, projects and networks.

3.1. Dissemination Strategy

Dissemination is a continuous chain of activities that must be adapted throughout the entire cycle of a research project. The project results should be publicly disseminated as soon as possible in accordance with the necessary restrictions on intellectual property protection, security rules, or legitimate interests.

The dissemination strategy of the REMODEL project is based on obtaining more research output. Based on six key questions (who, what, why, when, where and how), the strategy will identify key target groups and beneficiaries and define dissemination objectives, audience interests, and dissemination channels and tools. REMODEL's dissemination strategy focuses on providing a reliable, smooth and efficient information transfer.

REMODEL's dissemination strategy follows the main stages of the AIDA Method, known as the first advertising model. These stages are "Attention, Interest, Desire, and Action". In this project, first of all, awareness will be created to attract the attention of the target groups, so that the interest and desire of the target groups to learn more about the project and its activities will be ensured. Actions will then be taken to involve the target groups in the project and promote its results and facilitate their use.

In line with the dissemination strategy of the project, dissemination measures will be monitored, evaluated, regularly updated and reported by applying specific, measurable, accessible, relevant and time-related indicators that allow for improvement. The REMODEL project will adhere to open science, public participation and gender equality while disseminating its activities.

The full dissemination of REMODEL activities to the target user segments in Turkey will be realised by using the results and innovations produced through the BMI Lab throughout the project.

REMODEL will provide as many results, datasets and information as possible to as wide an audience as possible, following the Dissemination of knowledge within Horizon Europe's Key Impact Pathway on "Fostering diffusion of knowledge and open science".

3.2. Dissemination Objectives

The main goal of the REMODEL dissemination activities is to spread the project's main objectives, achievements and messages, and to maximise the project's impact at the European level. In particular, the main objective of disseminating REMODEL is to disseminate REMODEL results efficiently for successful exploitation and to prepare R&I incentives policy recommendations to Turkish funding and policy-making agencies.

The other objectives of the remodel project dissemination activities can be listed as follows:

- * Involving all stakeholders in project activities,
- * Obtaining all necessary evidence to define the REMODEL domain,
- * Development of special tools and applications envisaged in the BUU BMI Lab,
- * Correct execution of planned activities,
- * Ensuring the continuity and adoption of the project results,
- * Creating audience awareness and maximising impact on key stakeholders.

3.3. Dissemination Activities

The main dissemination activities and tools, together with their target groups and KPIs, are seen in the table below.

Table 3. Dissemination Activities and Tools

Dissemination Activities	Description	Due Date	Target Groups	KPIs
Website	www.projectremodel.eu	< March 2023 Continuous update	PM, RSC, IN-BP, IO	> 2.000 visitors
Scientific Publications	Publication of peer-reviewed, open access, in key top international	< December 2025	RSC	FWCI>1,4 per article 6 publications
Congresses, conferences	Project-related presentations in open access, qualified international conferences/ congresses with associated proceedings; organised by a university or a qualified institution	2023	RSC, PM, IN-BP	> 4 presentations at different events
		2024		> 2 presentations at different events
		2025		> 2 presentations at different events
Final Policy Brief	To support the uptake of REMODEL results and methodologies.	< December 2025	PM, RSC, IO	> 50 Download on the website
Liaison and Clustering Activities	Clustering activities	< December 2025	PM, IN-BP	>5 collaborations with national, regional or local institution or organisations
	Collaboration with EU-funded projects (sister projects)		RSC , IO	> 5 sister project

3.3.1. Scientific Publications

All staff of the REMODEL Project are highly prolific writers in scientific journals. Therefore, a significant number of high-impact scientific papers are expected to emerge from the project. These publications will apply green or gold Open Access models. These publications will include findings from various fields to ensure widespread dissemination of project developments and results. The consortium aims to produce at least six scientific journal papers. In this context, the project staff will publish journal papers that introduce the project as a whole, contain sectoral analysis and evaluate the purpose or results of the project in peer-reviewed well-known indexed journals during the execution of the project. The key performance of these publications is Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI) (intended to be at least 1.4 per article).

The publications on REMODEL results will help increase interest and awareness of the project and disseminate the main results of the project to the target groups. In addition, these publications will strengthen BUU's research capacity.

3.3.2. Congresses and Conferences

Participation in well-known and qualified international conferences is important in terms of disseminating the results of the project to a wider scientific audience and at the same time ensuring that the project is followed in the scientific community. Throughout the project, the REMODEL consortium partners will participate in conferences and deliver presentations to disseminate the project results and share insights with the broader communities within Europe and internationally.

REMODEL staff will attend at least eight different international conferences/congresses within the scope of project-related issues and present eight separate papers at esteemed international open-access conferences on tourism, business, management, humanities research, new business models, innovations in business, sustainable growth or social science innovations. These conferences can be hybrid. Virtual presentations are also useful for disseminating the results of the project and also contribute to the cost management of the project. However, physical conference attendance is preferred to ensure the desired interaction with other project staff or academics. Therefore, at least six of the conferences/congresses will be attended face-to-face.

3.3.3. Liaison and Clustering Activities

Common dissemination and collaboration of EU projects are necessary to maximise the outreach of the project. With liaison and clustering activities, it's aimed to cluster and collaborate with various associations, national authorities, regional authorities and local authorities related to the hospitality sector in order to provide information about the sector and to carry out the project activities effectively so that the REMODEL project can affect a much wider audience. Regular meetings are planned to be held at least every three months in order to ensure the continuity of collaboration with both public and private associations and organisations in the sector. These meetings will be held in the countries of each partner of the consortium, as well as joint meetings with the participation of all WP leaders from time to time.

In addition, collaboration with EU-funded projects related to REMODEL will be encouraged in order to create synergy and positive interactions. The REMODEL consortium is committed to capitalising on the results of relevant EU-funded projects. Clustering with related research projects helps to amplify common messages.

3.3.4. Policy Recommendations Brief

For generating the policy recommendations brief, the outcomes and achievements from the REMODEL project will be synthesized into actionable recommendations that are relevant to academic, industry, and governmental contexts. The primary focus is on providing a comprehensive set of policy recommendations that encourage SME participation in the hospitality sector in Türkiye, as well as offering research management recommendations for the academic community. We also determined relevant policymakers for each policy recommendations category. All progress and achievements will be included in the D5.3 Policy Recommendations Brief, ensuring that the document is comprehensive and targeted towards the appropriate policymakers.

D5.3 Policy Recommendations Brief will include:

* **Governmental Policy Recommendations:** Through active communication with the Turkish Ministry of Culture and Tourism as the key policy maker, we aim to ensure that our recommendations are also relevant and actionable at the governmental level. This includes insights gained from observing how ULE and ATU engage with SMEs and best practices in academic/industry linkages, which can be adapted and implemented in Türkiye.

* **Academic and Research Management Policy Recommendations:** Derived from the outputs of WP2 and WP3, these recommendations will focus on best practices in academic and research management, which can be adopted by universities and research institutions to foster innovation and collaboration with industry. The target policymaker in this area will be the Turkish Council of Higher Education, which is responsible for guiding education, teaching, and scientific research activities in universities across Türkiye. We will communicate with the Council to propose the dissemination of the Academic and Research Management Policy developed within the REMODEL project to other universities in Turkey.

* **Industry-Specific Policy Recommendations:** Utilizing the Business Model Innovation (BMI) Framework, these recommendations will address the specific needs of SMEs in the Turkish hospitality sector, providing strategies for growth, innovation, and sustainability. The target policymakers in this area will be GÜMTOB (Southern Marmara Tourist Hoteliers and Operators Association), the Bursa Provincial Directorate of Culture and Tourism, and the Bursa Metropolitan Municipality. Through these policymakers, we aim to adapt and implement the policy recommendations for the BMI framework in local and regional application areas.

4. COMMUNICATION PLAN

In the most general terms, communication is the sending and receiving of information between people in groups or one-on-one. A communication plan is a structured approach used to provide information to various target groups. The detailed communication plan records who should receive what information, when this information should be provided, and which channels should be used for this purpose. In the REMODEL communication plan, it is recommended that all activities carried out within the scope of the project are conveyed to the target groups in a timely and accurate manner. It is important to reach more target groups through different communication channels and to present information in a striking way with user-friendly tools. REMODEL builds its communication plan in line with this strategy.

4.1. Communication Strategy

A communication strategy is a plan to deliver a message to your predetermined target groups. The REMODEL communication strategy will be defined at the very beginning of the project providing specific Communication Guidelines (D5.1) with common actions and

milestones implemented within the project span, ensuring the broadest impact on the targeted audience, as well as including the project branding guide (Book of Style). Guidelines will also provide a list of Communication Contact Points (appointed by each partner organisation) to be in charge of implementing the Strategy under the coordination of the Communication Manager (BUU).

An exhaustive and detailed procedure aimed at following up and monitoring the Strategy implementation will be defined, so that the low impact of any action can be anticipated at an early stage, and appropriate corrective actions set up.

The main purpose of the REMODEL communication strategy is to establish a systematic approach for the communication activities that support the objectives of the project. The REMODEL communication strategy will serve as an overall approach for the consortium communication activities. It will enable the project to reach the target groups more and increase the impact of the project's effects on the target groups.

4.2. Communication Objectives

The main purpose of REMODEL communication objective is to announce the main objectives, achievements, and messages of the project to the target groups with the right communication tools and enhance the impact of the project at the European level. Other purposes of the communication objectives of the REMODEL project can be listed as follows: of the Communication Manager (BUU).

4.3. Communication Activities and Key Performance Indicators

The main communication activities and tools, together with their target groups and KPIs, are as seen in the table below.

Table 4. Communication Activities and Tools

Communication Activities	Description	Due Date	Target	KPIs
Website	https://projectremodel.eu	< March 2023 and regular updates	PM, IO, RSC, IN-BP	> 2.000 visitors
Social Media Accounts	LinkedIn	< March 2023 and regular updates	RSC, PM, IO, IN-BP, CS	>500 followers and views and 50 posts
	Instagram			>500 followers and views and 50 posts
	Twitter			>200 followers and views and 50 posts
	YouTube			> 5 videos with 100 views per video
E-newsletters	E-newsletters issued half-yearly to ensure a regular flow of information to specific target groups.	August 2023 January 2024 August 2024 January 2025 August 2025 December 2025	RSC, PM, IO, IN-BP, CS	6 e-Newsletters, > 50 clicks on the website
Promotional Video	Showcasing the REMODEL concept, BMI labs SME engagement, and expected impacts	January 2024	CS	1 promotional video with > 40 comments
Short Videos	* Interviews * Motion graphics * Animations (explaining key project messages and BMI lab in an easy language.)	January 2024 July 2024 November 2024 May 2025 November 2025	CS	> 5 short videos with > 40 comments
Media Appearance	* Press Release	January 2023 September 2024 September 2025	PM, RSC, IN-BP	3 press release
	* Articles (the tools offered by the EC)	April 2023 December 2024 November 2025		3 articles by each partner

Communication Activities	Description	Due Date	Target	KPIs
Other Communication Tools and Materials	Posters	January 2023 (4) December 2024 September 2025	PM, IO, RSC, IN- BP	6 posters
	Brochures	January 2023 February 2024 December 2024 November 2025		4 Brochures
	Roll-up	January 2023		1 roll- up
	Foam Board	May 2024		1 Foam Board
	Podcasts	March 2025 November 2025		2 podcasts
	Leaflets	> December 2024		>16 leaflets
	Infographics	September 2025 (2)		2 infographics
	Factsheets	December 2023 (2) March 2024 October 2025		4 factsheets
	Booklets	April 2023 October 2024 July 2025		3 booklets

4.3.1. Remodel Website

REMODEL project website with public and internal areas was delivered at the end of February 2023. A user-friendly and accessible website was designed and deployed following the project book of style. The target group of the REMODEL website can be listed as policy makers and innovation agencies, scientific and technical communities, industry and especially researchers.

On this website, at least 30 news items should be published with 2.000 visitors by the end of the project. The REMODEL website is hosted at <https://projectremodel.eu>. As the project progresses, the website will post regular updates upon suggestion by the consortium.

The REMODEL website is presented in Figure 2 and contains the following menu and features in Table 4.

Table 5. REMODEL Website Menu

Home	About	News & Events	Training	Results	Liaison and Clustering Activities	Contact
	Project Work Packages Consortium Project Management Project Team		Capacity Building Training Summer Schools Staff Exchange	Deliverables Milestones Publications Project Materials Scientific Congress/ Conference	Sister Projects Interaction with Organisations and Institutions	

Figure 2. The REMODEL Project LinkedIn Account

4.3.2. Social Media Accounts

Social Media Accounts, with their constant use and account updates, ensure the participation of the community and the accessibility and visibility of the REMODEL platform. In particular, social media accounts will be used to inform stakeholders about project activities and results, to raise broad public awareness, to encourage a discussion about needed changes in the industry, and to actively involve identified target groups in envisaged activities. Different types of social networks selected by the partners will be used to reach specific target groups. Remodel social networks are LinkedIn, Instagram, Twitter and YouTube.

Table 6. Social Media Accounts

Communication Activity Name	Description	Target Groups	Communication Channel	KPI
LinkedIn (LI)	the LinkedIn Remodel Project account (https://www.linkedin.com/in/remodel-project-933904259/)	RSC, PM, IO, IN-BP, CS	Social media	> 500 followers, > 500 views and at least 50 posts
Instagram (IG)	@remodel_project Instagram account (https://www.instagram.com/remodel_project/)	RSC, PM, IO, IN-BP, CS	Social media	> 500 followers, > 500 views and at least 50 posts
Twitter (TW)	the @Project_Remodel Twitter account (https://twitter.com/project_remodel)	RSC, PM, IO, IN-BP, CS	Social media	> 200 followers, > 200 views and at least 50 posts
YouTube (YT)	@RemodelProject YouTube account (https://www.youtube.com/@RemodelProject)	RSC, PM, IO, IN-BP, CS	Social media	> 5 videos and 100 views per video

Hashtags are essential for social media management. Hashtags allow expanding reach by creating searchable keywords or phrases. The hashtags that are planned to be used most in REMODEL social media accounts are as follows and additional hashtags for events or shared content will also be identified:

#RemodelProject, #Remodel, #sustainabletourism, #innovativebusinessmodels, #BMILab, #BUUBMILab, #innovation, #HorizonEurope #Widera, #twinning

4.3.2.1. LinkedIn

The LinkedIn account of the REMODEL project will be used for announcements regarding project activities, meetings, visits, etc. which will be shared in order to increase the visibility and awareness of the REMODEL project.

On the REMODEL LinkedIn account, at least 50 posts should be shared, at least 500 followers and at least 500 views achieved by the end of the project.

The REMODEL LinkedIn account is presented in Figure 3 and hosted at <https://www.linkedin.com/in/remodel-project-933904259/>.

Figure 3. The REMODEL Project LinkedIn Account

The screenshot shows the LinkedIn profile for the REMODEL Project. The profile is set to 'Public' and is located in Bursa, Bursa, Turkey. It is funded by the European Union and has 337 connections. The profile picture features a gear and a globe, and the cover image shows a globe with blue light trails. The profile is associated with Uludağ Üniversitesi and Bursa Uludag University. The analytics section shows 228 profile views, 373 post impressions, and 10 search appearances.

Remodel Project
 Funded by the European Union
 Bursa, Bursa, Turkey · [Contact info](#)
 337 connections

[Open to](#) [Add profile section](#) [More](#)

Analytics
 Private to you

Analytics Category	Value	Description
Profile Views	228	Discover who's viewed your profile.
Post Impressions	373	Check out who's engaging with your posts.
Search Appearances	10	See how often you appear in search results.

4.3.2.2. Instagram

The Instagram account of REMODEL Project will also be used for announcements regarding, project activities, meetings, visits, etc. which will be shared in order to increase the visibility and awareness of the REMODEL project.

On this Remodel Instagram account, at least 50 posts should be shared, at least 500 followers achieved and at least 500 views by the end of the project.

Remodel Instagram account is presented in Figure 4 and hosted at https://www.instagram.com/remodel_project/.

Figure 4. The REMODEL Project Instagram Account

4.3.2.4. YouTube

The YouTube account of REMODEL project will be used as an online video repository for all videos produced by the project. However, the possibility to organise live streaming with experts will be considered.

On this REMODEL YouTube account, at least 5 videos should be shared and at least 100 views per video achieved by the end of the project.

Remodel YouTube account is presented in Figure 6 and hosted at <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXpCS9SeHELOebX37QaR3TQ>.

Figure 6. The REMODEL Project YouTube Account

4.3.3. E-Newsletters

E-newsletters will be issued to ensure a regular flow of information to specific target groups. The target groups of the REMODEL e-newsletter can be listed as policy makers, research and scientific communities, international organisations and institutions, industry and business partners and civil society.

A total of six e-newsletters will be prepared twice a year during the REMODEL project and should achieve at least 50 clicks on the website for each e-newsletter.

The first e-newsletter will be published in August 2023, including project information, kick-off meeting and activities in the first six months. The second e-newsletter will be published in January 2024, including workshops, summer schools, certificate program, staff exchanges and conference presentations in 2023. The third e-newsletter will be published in August 2024, including hospitality sector analysis, BMI Lab workings and activities. The fourth e-newsletter will be published in January 2025, including workshops, summer schools, certificate program, staff exchanges, and conference presentations in 2024. The fifth e-newsletter will be published in August 2025, including publications, BMI Lab workings and activities. The last e-newsletter will be published in December 2025, including workshops, summer schools, staff exchanges, conference presentations in 2025 and final meeting.

Table 7. E-Newsletter Activities

Communication Activity Name	Description	Target Group	Due Date	KPIs
E-Newsletter 1	Project Information, Kick off Meeting, Activities	PM, IO, RSC, IN-BP, CS	August 2023	at least 50 clicks on the website
E-Newsletter 2	Workshops, Summer School, Certificate Program and Staff Exchange, Conference Presentations in 2023	PM, IO, RSC, IN-BP, CS	January 2024	at least 50 clicks on the website
E-Newsletter 3	Hospitality Sector Analysis, BMI Lab workings, Activities	PM, IO, RSC, IN-BP, CS	August 2024	at least 50 clicks on the website

Communication Activity Name	Description	Target Group	Communication Channel	KPIs
E-Newsletter 4	Workshops, Summer School, Certificate Program and Staff Exchange, Conference Presentations in 2024	PM, IO, RSC, IN-BP, CS	January 2025	at least 50 clicks on the website
E-Newsletter 5	Publications, BMI Lab workings, Activities	PM, IO, RSC, IN-BP, CS	August 2025	at least 50 clicks on the website
E-Newsletter 6	Workshops, Summer School and Staff Exchange, Conference Presentations in 2025, Final Meeting	PM, IO, RSC, IN-BP, CS	December 2025	at least 50 clicks on the website

4.3.4. Videos

Within the scope of the REMODEL project, a promotional video and at least 5 short videos will be produced. BUU will produce one promotional video (M12) presenting the REMODEL's concept, the BUU BMI Lab, and expected impacts in December 2023. This promotional video should receive more than 40 comments.

In addition, during the WP4 implementation phase in cooperation with SMEs in the hospitality sector, a series of factsheets and short videos (describing the activities and targeting local communities) will be produced by BUU to be widely promoted, especially through social networks. During the last quarter of the project, short videos linked to main project outcomes will be also produced.

Short videos will be prepared in the form of interviews, motion graphics, animations to explain the key project messages and the BMI Lab in an easy language. The videos will be adapted to the REMODEL target groups and made available on-line through social networks, website, communication campaigns or presentations in related events. Each of the short videos should receive more than 40 comments.

4.3.5. Media Appearance

During the project, with using some media channels the REMODEL project will disseminate to all stakeholders by press releases and EC communication routes.

4.3.6. Other Online and Printed Communication Materials

During the project, different online or printed communication tools other than the ones listed above can be used. These are primarily planned as posters, brochures, roll-up, leaflets and podcast. However, different tools can be used within the scope of the project, if necessary.

These tools will be used to support communication activities :

- **Posters:** REMODEL Overall Methodology, REMODEL WPs, BMI Lab, Capacity Building Training activities, BMI Lab Activities, REMODEL Results
- **Brochures:** REMODEL Introduction, Capacity Building Training activities, BMI Lab processes, REMODEL results
- **Podcasts:** Introduction of REMODEL activities and content
- **Roll-up:** REMODEL introduction
- **Foam Board:** Portable REMODEL and BMI Lab logo
- **Leaflets:** Online Training Leaflets
- **Infographics:** General information about the project activities and Activities of the BMI Lab
- **Booklets:** REMODEL Introduction for stakeholders, Business & Leadership Program and Summer Schools
- **Factsheets:** Introduction, REMODEL Training Activities, Evaluation of the Hospitality Sector in Turkey and Results of Scientific Studies

5. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ROLE ALLOCATION

To ensure the smooth and efficient execution of dissemination and communication activities, REMODEL partners have established a coordinated role allocation and defined a timeline for the use of tools.

Table 8. REMODEL Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Role Allocation and Time Schedule

	LEAD	Jan. 23	Feb. 23	Mar. 23	Apr. 23	May. 23	June 23	July 23	Aug. 23	Sep. 23	Oct. 23	Nov. 23	Dec. 23
Roll-up	BUU												
Press Release 1	BUU												
Poster 1	BUU												
Poster 2	BUU												
Poster 3	BUU												
Poster 4	BUU												
Brochure 1	BUU												
Website	BUU												
Social Media Accounts	BUU												
Booklet 1	BUU												
Newsletter 1	BUU												
Project Factsheet	BUU												
Factsheet 2	BUU												
Leaflets	BUU												

	LEAD	Jan. 24	Feb. 24	Mar. 24	Apr. 24	May .24	June. 24	July. 24	Aug. 24	Sep. 24	Oct. 24	Nov. 24	Dec. 24
Promotional Video	BUU												
Video 1	BUU												
Newsletter 2	BUU												
Brochure 2	ULE+ BUU												
Factsheet 3	BUU												
Article 1	ULE												
Foam Board	BUU												
Video 2	ULE												
Newsletter 3	BUU												
Press Release 2	BUU												
Booklet 2	ATU												
Video 3	ATU												
Poster 5	BUU												
Brochure 3	ATU+ BUU												
Article 2	ATU												
Leaflets	BUU												

	LEAD	Jan. 25	Feb. 25	Mar. 25	Apr. 25	May. 25	June. 25	July. 25	Aug. 25	Sep. 25	Oct. 25	Nov. 25	Dec. 25
Newsletter 4	BUU												
Podcast 1	ULE												
Video 4	BUU												
Booklet 3	ULE												
Newsletter 5	BUU												
Infographic 1	ATU												
Infographic 2	BUU												
Press Release 3	BUU												
Poster 6	BUU												
Factsheet 4	ULE												
Video 5	BUU												
Brochure 4	BUU												
Podcast 2	ATU												
Article 3	BUU												
Newsletter 6	BUU												

6. EXPLOITATION PLAN

Exploitation is the process of using project results in further research and innovation activities or standardisation activities to develop, create, manufacture and market a product or process and to provide a service, including commercial activities. The primary aim of the exploitation is to utilise the project accomplishments for societal, scientific, and financial objectives.

Within the scope of REMODEL Exploitation, it is planned to prepare a sustainable business model for the BMI Laboratory and to design a voucher system by calculating operational costs and expenditures and anticipated revenues. The business model will consider the possibility of implementing a publicly funded innovation incentive system that can facilitate Turkish SMEs' access to the laboratory by leveraging existing systems in the twinning partners' countries.

The consortium designed a roadmap to constitute the permanent network resulting from the project. Accordingly, all partners will establish interactions with public authorities at EU and national levels, to exchange information on available or planned public or public-private requirements and guidelines and will promote the exchange of information on good practices for R&I incentives among the twinning countries and Turkey.

6.1. Exploitation Strategy

The REMODEL project has been designed to respond to a genuine need in all countries to support SMEs in the Hospitality sector through knowledge transfer. The project activities are based on strengthening links with regional, national and international stakeholders. To this end, the REMODEL consortium has been formed by partners that will ensure the participation of a wide stakeholder group and the promotion of the project in the relevant countries and affected markets and sectors. REMODEL's exploitation strategy is to maximise the outputs and long-term effects of the project and to ensure the sustainability of the project results.

The plans that align with this strategy will provide a comprehensive and practical path for the project's success. First of all, the relevant target groups will be determined within the scope of exploitation with stakeholder analysis. Afterward, the basic framework of the collaborations to be established with the stakeholders will be established, and research paths, funding sources and application areas will be determined. Thus, even after the project is completed, BUU R&I capacity, which has increased with REMODEL, will continue to strengthen and businesses in the sector will continue to benefit from the innovative business models created within the scope of the Project.

6.2. Exploitation Objectives

The main purpose of REMODEL exploitation activities is to facilitate the access of SMEs in Turkey to the BUU BMI laboratory. In line with this purpose, BUU TTO will promote the activities of the BMI laboratory and maintain its sustainability after the project's closure.

The other objectives of the REMODEL project exploitation activities can be listed as follows:

- * To encourage new projects at both the national and EU levels.
- * Leveraging the expertise of BUU staff by increasing their research capacity to mobilise new projects at the national and EU levels.
- * Using project results to benefit SMEs operating in the hospitality sector.
- * Providing seminars and consultancy activities to SMEs in all partners' countries.
- * Ensuring that project outputs are used across the EU with Ireland's broad stakeholder network.
- * Promoting the voucher system for SMEs in the hospitality sector in Turkey.
- * Establishing new collaboration with national, regional and local organisations, associations and administrations for the hospitality sector in Turkey.
- * To utilise the project results in further research and PhD or master thesis related to REMO-

6.3. Exploitation Activities and Key Performance Indicators

The main exploitation activities and tools, together with their target group and KPIs, are seen in the table below.

Table 9. Exploitation Activities and Tools

Exploitation Activities	Description	Target Group	KPIs
To Encourage new projects at both the national and EU levels	In particular, the increased relevance and reputation gained through the execution of REMODEL will be the seed to coordinate novel proposals at HEU and other EU-funded programmes.	IO, RSC	Applying at least 3 EU-Funded Projects
Maintaining and promoting the activities of the BUU BMI Lab. in collaboration with BUU TTO	The REMODEL Lab will stay sustainable after the closure of the project by the voucher system which will be managed by the BUU TTO and connect the companies and the Lab.	IN-BP, RSC	Maintaining the effective activities of the BMI Lab for at least 3 more years after the end of the project
Collaboration with the Chamber of Commerce of León	The results of this project will also benefit SMEs in the hospitality sector in León, through the collaboration of the Chamber of Commerce of León.	PM, IN-BP	3 events organised together
Seminars and Workshop	Seminars or workshops will be provided to SMEs as well as consultancy activities to help SMEs to adapt their business models.	IN-BP	1 seminar or workshop
Continuing to publish news about REMODEL results on universities' websites	Communication of the project will be provided through the BUU, ULE and ATU websites to attract more stakeholders.	PM, IO, IN-BP, RSC	> 3 news per year 50 clicks per news

Exploitation Activities	Description	Target Group	KPIs
Collaboration with national, regional and local organisations, associations and administrations in Turkey	The project outputs are likely to be referenced and used after funding ceases and generates a long-term impact in Turkey.	PM	> 3 active continuations of collaboration in Turkey
Meetings with academic staff	Meetings will be held with the academic staff at ULE, BUU, and ATU to ensure that the project results are used in different universities for the development of all students and young researchers.	RSC	> 3 academic staff for each university 5 students per year
Support to the REMODEL from all external stakeholders	To increase the interest and support of external stakeholders such as economic development agencies and local governments in the project. Thus, by having the project outputs referenced and used even after the funding ends, creating a long-term impact in Ireland and even across the EU.	PM, IO	> 3 active continuations of collaboration in Ireland
Launching a Master's Degree Programme at BUU	A joint Master in Business Innovation for the Hospitality Sector will be launched at BUU.	RSC	> 7 students per year
Producing doctoral and master's thesis related to REMODEL project results	Reach out to the Ph.D. students and formulate thesis proposals to utilise the project results in further research.	RSC	> > 3 PhD thesis > 5 Master thesis

7. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY (IP) PROTECTION

REMODEL establishes its DEC strategy, adhering to the FAIR data principles and guidance of the EC's open-access conferences and journals, to ensure that those working on other EU projects benefit from the outputs and make progress. Within the scope of this project, the results of the project such as scientific publications, and sector analysis should be disclosed to the public in appropriate ways. Also, the project results will be used in further research and activities for commercial purposes such as the development and marketing of a product or process and the creation of a service. Accordingly, the joint owners must agree in writing on the allocation and terms of the exercise of their joint ownership to ensure compliance with their obligations. If third parties (including employees and other personnel) may claim rights to the results, the beneficiary concerned must ensure that those rights can be exercised in a manner compatible with its obligations under the Agreement.

If materials or documents are subject to moral rights or third-party rights (including intellectual property rights or rights of natural persons on their image and voice), the beneficiaries must ensure that they comply with their obligations (in particular, by obtaining the necessary licences and authorisations from the rights holders concerned). A beneficiary aiming to disseminate its results must notify other project beneficiaries at least 15 days before the information and results from it will disseminate unless otherwise agreed. If the beneficiary can also show his/her legitimate interests regarding the information or results presented in the project will be significantly harmed, he/she can object within 15 days of receiving the notification and the dissemination of the results will be stopped unless otherwise agreed.

The EC attaches importance to IP protection to secure the social and economic benefits of innovations arising from R&I projects and recognises that strong IP protection can be an essential element of a successful business strategy. As part of the IP protection strategy of this project, all commercially sensitive innovations are protected for consortium members, in line with the EC's objectives for IP protection.

Activities related to IPR will be reported on a six-monthly basis, except for emergencies, and will be coordinated at the Project Steering Group level. These reports will include specific provisions for the ownership of IPR by consortium members and the granting of licences and the management of IPR will be governed by the CA.

8. MONITORING

All dissemination and communication activities will be continuously monitored and reported in each reporting period based on the evaluation procedure. A monitoring mechanism will be established with the specific purpose of monitoring the progress and outcomes of this plan. The continuous evaluation of the strategy is crucial to ensure its effectiveness and to revise or redefine it as necessary. Monitoring progress is measured using both quantitative and qualitative indicators for each activity. As the strategy is updated, the data on achievements will be enhanced. Monitoring the dissemination and communication activities is important for the internal control of the project.

The WP5 leader will be responsible for frequent monitoring of the dissemination and communication strategy and will collaborate with partners to determine the next steps. Also a monitoring table will be prepared and all partners complete the table before each two-month period.

Table 10. Remodel DEC Activities Monitoring Table

Date	Activity	Partner Lead / Involved	Target Group	KPIs

REMODEL will monitor defined KPIs for:

- * Scientific Publications
- * Attended Conferences
- * Website and Social Media Accounts
- * Training Activities
- * Collaborations
- * E- Newsletter
- * Videos
- * Other communication and dissemination tools (factsheets, infographics etc.)

For verification of DEC activities of this project; attendance lists, meeting minutes, photos, statistics (website analytics and social media metrics) and reports will be prepared. Additionally, according to Task 5.3 Liaison and clustering activities, at 18 and 36 months a “Communication, dissemination, exploitation, liaison, and clustering report” will be prepared.

9. PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY

For the visual identity of REMODEL initially a visual identity guide was prepared to give correct instructions and examples of logo and Typography usage. This guide includes the template of the documents or PowerPoint and the information about EU acknowledgement.

The most obvious identity of a project is its logo. The REMODEL logo is designed to reflect the fusion of business and innovation. The colours are chosen in the most harmonious eye-catching shades of yellow and blue, which are innovative colours. It consists of two parts. One is the symbol and the other one is the wordmark. Remodel Logo is designed as follows:

REMODEL colour palette consists of cyan blue and yellowish orange main colours. Horizontal and monochromatic logos are also designed for use in different places and materials. They are designed as follows:

Another important visual that will be used in all documents, presentations and materials during the project is the EU Emblem. This emblem is the only visual identity used to highlight EU support and ensure the visibility of EU funding.

The project's partners should include the European flag and the funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate), accepting the EU support in all communication activities related to the project. The EU emblem must be easily visible with its EU corporate blue and yellow colours. In this respect, attention should be paid to the size, position, colour and quality of the emblem. The font colour should be Reflex Blue or white-black depending on the background. Horizontal or monochromatic logos can be selected depending on where they will be used.

EU support must be indicated for all social media, posters, brochures or any equipment used and financed in dissemination and communication activities within the scope of the REMODEL project. In addition, the text and equipment used for the project should include the European flag (emblem) and the funding statement.

For the visual identity, the typography of the project was identified. The font used in the logo is Azonix for being striking. The font for all text, from body text to headline, is primarily Arial. Arial is a corporate typeface that plays an important role in transmitting energy and enthusiasm. Also, the typeface to be used in conjunction with the EU emblem is Arial. The secondary font is Times New Roman. The reason why Times New Roman is preferred as a secondary font is; it is the default font of many programs. The full "Project Branding and Visual Identity Guide" is detailed in Annex 1.

Annex 1. Project Branding & Visual Identity Guide

Funded by
the European Union

PROJECT BRANDING & VISUAL IDENTITY GUIDE

universidad
de león

Óifiscoil
Teicneolaíochta
an Atlantaigh
Atlantic
Technological
University

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INTRODUCTION

This guide represents the visual identity of REMODEL Project. REMODEL is a project, which aims to strengthen BUU R&I capacity and skills through leveraging the experience and state-of-the-art knowledge and digital tools made available by twinning partners ULE and ATU in business model innovation. The project has been funded by the European Union under the call of HORIZON-WIDERA-2021- ACCESS-03.

This guide aims to give correct instructions and examples of logo and TYPOGRAPHY usage. In this guide you can find the template of the documents or powerpoints and the informations about EU acknowledgement. In addition poster, brochure and roll-up banner examples are given in this guide for explaining the visual design.

REMODEL

LOGO

Standart Logo

Standart logo is the main logo for general use. It consists of two parts. One is the symbol and the other one is the wordmark.

The REMODEL logo is designed to reflect the fusion of business and innovation. The colors are chosen in the most harmonious eye-catching shades of yellow and blue, which are innovation colors.

This section provides guidelines on how to use the logo in any format, including the recommended type of face, color palette.

REMODEL

LOGO

Alternative Logo (Horizontal Use)

The alternative logo is the horizontal version of the main logo. It may be used when the space is wide and limited.

REMODEL

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LOGO

Monochromatic Logo

Monochromatic Logo Design is a type of design created using one colour. Monochrome version logos are designed for use in color-restricted applications or colorless prints.

REMODEL

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LOGO

~~REMODEL~~

REMODEL

Incorrect Use of Logo

- Don't delete any portion of the logo
- Don't use non-approved or altered colours.
- Don't alter the logo symbol and type style
- Don't change size relationship between the logo and logo type.
- Don't change the proportions of the logo vertically/horizontally.

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LOGO

Primary Colour Palette for the Logo

REMODEL colour palette consists of **CYAN BLUE** and **YELLOWISH ORANGE** main colours.

However, monochromatic logo can be used in colorless printing and applications. It is important that the logo is visible.

**CYAN
BLUE**

**YELLOWISH
ORANGE**

CMYK

C 92 M 63
Y 01 K 00

C 12 M 38
Y 74 K 00

RGB

R 00 G 99
B 176

R 223 G 163
B 91

HEX

#0063b0

#dfa35b

REMODEL

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LOGO

Background

The preferred background colour for the REMODEL Logo is white.

It is used with a white circle under the logo so that the logo is visible on images or colored backgrounds.

Monochrome logos on images or colored backgrounds are appropriate. Black logo on light backgrounds. White logo is preferred on dark backgrounds.

REMODEL

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LOGO

Minimum Size

The minimum size of the full logo should be 3.80 cm to 4.00 cm

The minimum size of the logo symbol should be 29 mm to 24 mm.

REMODEL

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PROJECT PARTNERS LOGOS

Standart Partners Logos

The logos of the project partners are:

universidad
de león

Ollscoil
Teicneolaíochta
an Atlantaigh

Atlantic
Technological
University

REMODEL

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PROJECT PARTNERS LOGOS

Monochromatic Logos of Partners

Monochromatic logos to be used on colored/illustrated backgrounds or colorless printing or applications are:

universidad
de león

Ollscoil
Teicneolaíochta
an Atlantaigh

Atlantic
Technological
University

REMODEL

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USE OF EU LOGO

Funded by
the European Union

The EU emblem is the only visual identity used to highlight EU support and ensure the visibility of EU funding.

The partners of the project should include the European flag and the funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate) accepting the EU support in all communication activities related to the project.

The EU emblem must be easily visible. In this respect, attention should be paid to the size, position, color and quality of the emblem.

The EU emblem must not be altered or combined with any other graphic elements or text. If other logos are displayed in addition to the EU emblem, the emblem must be at least the same size as the largest of the other logos.

Sufficient contrast should be provided between the EU emblem and the background.

The colour of the font should be Reflex Blue or white-black depending on the background.

REMODEL

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USE OF EU LOGO

Association of the EU Emblem with the Funding Statement Horizontal Option

**Funded by
the European Union**

Monochromatic Horizontal Option

**Funded by
the European Union**

REMODEL

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USE OF EU LOGO

Association of the EU Emblem with
the Funding Statement Vertical
Option

Funded by
the European Union

Monochromatic Vertical
Option

Funded by
the European Union

REMODEL

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USE OF EU LOGO

Colour Palette

EU Corporate Blue

C: 100 | M: 80 | Y: 0 | K: 0 R: 0 | G: 51 | B: 153 #003399

Yellow 100%

C: 0 | M: 0 | Y: 100 | K: 0 R: 255 | G: 204 | B: 0 #FFCC00

Minimum Size

The minimum height of the EU emblem must be 1 cm (except pens, stickers etc.). When using the EU funding statement in a small size the horizontal version should be used.

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TYPOGRAPHY

Logo Font of Remodel

REMODEL

The font used in the logo is **Azonix**

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

01234567789

= * @ ? & ! % + / # -

REMODEL

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TYPOGRAPHY

Alternative Typography

The secondary font is **Times New Roman**.

The reason why **Times New Roman** is preferred as a secondary font; It is the default font of many programs.

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

01234567789

= * @ ? & ! % + / # -

REMODEL

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POWERPOINT TEMPLATE

The Title Page

The recommended font on ppt is Arial and maximum font size is 60pt.

Subheadings are 36pt.

The slide features a central 'Title' placeholder. To the left is a blue vertical bar and the REMODEL logo. To the right is an orange vertical bar and the European Union logo with the text 'Funded by the European Union'. At the bottom are logos for Universidad de León, Universidad de León, and Atlantic Technological University.

POWERPOINT TEMPLATE

Content Page

The headline size is 42 pt and body text size is 28pt.

The slide features a central content area with a 'Title' placeholder and a large text block containing placeholder text: "Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum." A gear icon is positioned in the top right corner of the content area. The REMODEL logo is visible in the bottom left and bottom center.

POWERPOINT TEMPLATE

Content Page

The headline size is 42 pt and body text size is 28pt.

Title

"Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum."

REMODEL

REMODEL

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EU ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Social media, poster, etc. communication activities, dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment etc. output financed by the grant related to REMODEL, EU support should be acknowledged and the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages where appropriate) should be displayed.

REMODEL

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EU ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

It should state the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate): “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

In addition, the following statement should be included in all documents and communication channels: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101079203.”